

MYXOMYCETES RECORDS FROM NATIONAL PARK “GOMOLSHA FORESTS” (UKRAINE)

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National Park “Gomolsha Forests” is situated in the North-West of Ukraine, in the forest-steppe zone. During 2000-2004, it was found 119 species of Myxomycetes from 33 genera, 9 families and 6 orders. Between the orders, Physarales includes 30.5% of found species, Trichiales – 25.4%, Stemonitales – 22.9%, Liceales – 19.5%.

All of found species can be considered as the new for the Gomolsha Forests, and many ones are new for the bigger territories. Thus 52 species are new for Left-bank forest-steppe of Ukraine, and 31 species are new for Ukraine. Last are *Licea tenera* E.Jahn, *Lycogala exiguum* Morgan, *Lycogala terrestre* Fr., *Reticularia intermedia* Nann.-Bremek., *Reticularia splendens* Morgan, *Tubulifera microsperma* (Berk. & M.A.Curtis) Lado, *Cribraria intricata* Schrad., *Arcyria affinis* Rostaf., *Arcyria helvetica* (Meyl.) H.Neubert, Nowotny, K.Baumann, *Arcyria minuta* Buchet in Patouliar, *Arcyria stipata* (Schwein.) Lister, *Collaria biasperospora* (Kowalski) Dhillon & Nann.-Bremek. ex Ing, *Comatricha alta* Preuss, *Lamproderma scintillans* (Berk. & Broome) Morgan, *Stemonaria fuscoidea* Nann.-Bremek. & Y.Yamam., *Stemonitis rhizoideipes* Nann.-Bremek., R.Sharma & K.S.Thind in Nann.-Bremek., Y.Yamam. & R.Sharma, *Symphytocarpus flaccidus* (Lister) B.Ing & Nann.-Bremek., *Badhamia gracilis* (T.Macbr.) T.Macbr., *Fuligo candida* Pers., *Fuligo laeviderma* H.Neubert, Nowotny, K.Baumann, *Physarum confertum* T.Macbr., *Physarum pusillum* (Berk. & M.A.Curtis) G.Lister in Lister, *Physarum serpula* Morgan, *Physarum vernum* Sommerf. in Fr., *Diderma deplanatum* Fr., *Diderma effusum* (Schwein.) Morgan, *Diderma montanum* (Meyl.) Meyl., *Didymium dubium* Rostaf., *Didymium iridis* (Ditmar) Fr., *Didymium minus* (Lister) Morgan

Several specimens are of the especial interest. Thus the specimen CWU MT058 definitely corresponds to the diagnosis of *Trichia agaves* (Moreno, Lizerraga, Illara) Lado. Very characteristic is extremely thin capillitium (2.5 µm diam.) still having the distinct spiral ornamentation. Also recognizable is areolate two-layers peridium. Very strange is the find of this recently described tropical species in deciduous forest of moderate zone, on the bark of *Quercus robur* L. Another unusual specimen CWU ML103 is similar to *Licea iridis* Ing & McHugh. It has clearly iridescent peridium, dark-brown warted spores 10-11 µm and other diagnostic features of *L.iridis*, but has two times larger sporangia (0.6 mm diam.) and was found on mosses.

Some aspects of the plant community preferences of Myxomycetes species in Gomolsha Forests were investigated. Correlations between occurrence patterns of 22 widespread species were calculated. Species with correlating occurrences appeared to form 6 distinct groups. 90.9% of analyzed species are involved in these groups. Each group consists from 2 to 6 species, all or almost all of which are connected by strong correlations, and there is no significant correlation between different groups and their individual members. The belonging of a species to preference group is not the same as belonging to certain community; it indicates a definiteness of a place of species in the given community, e.g. dominant, subdominant, outsider etc. It was shown that species, belonging to the same preference group, develop mainly on different substrata (wood, bark, litter etc.). Possibly that is the way to avoid a competition. In those rare cases, when such species occur on one substratum type, they appear to be representatives of the distant taxonomic groups. This confirms the statement of STEPHENSON (1988), that the competition between related species of Myxomycetes is stronger, than between unrelated.

Year-to-year dynamics of Myxomycetes in Gomolsha Forests has shown the coordinated fluctuation in sporulation activity of some genera in the field conditions. For example, *Trichia* species sporulate most actively in the years with low abundance of *Arcyria*, and vice versa.